

NODES – Nord Ovest Digitale e Sostenibile

FLAGSHIP PROJECT GRIP

SPOKE 2 – GREEN TECHNOLOGIES AND SUSTAINABLE INDUSTRIES

DELIVERABLE D7.6: Biomaterials for bioactive extracts delivery

REPORTING PERIOD	
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RM7 Responsible	Stefano Superchi

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Glossary

	Definition
Hub Coordinator (HC)	The Hub Coordinator represents the single point of contact for the implementation of the innovation ecosystem towards the MUR. It carries out the management and coordination activities of the innovation ecosystem, receives the fundings, verifies, and transmits to the MUR the reporting of the activities carried out by the Spoke and their affiliates.
National Recovery and Resilience Plan (NRRP)	This document uses the Italian acronym for the NRRP, which is PNRR (Piano Nazionale della Ripresa e Resilienza)
Research Program Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the overall scientific contents of the NODES project. The NODES will appoint the Research Program Manager. It refers to "Responsabile del Programma di Ricerca" in the MUR's Call of proposal for "Ecosistemi di Innovazione"
NODES' Research and innovation program	NODES' Research and Innovation program is articulated in specific programs for each Spoke, with the aim to promote and support applied research on topics consistent with the Intelligent Specialization Strategy, with the guidelines of the 2021-2027 partnership agreement scheme, with regional operational plans and regional and national research and innovation priorities. Although NODES' Spokes are concentrated on different themes, they will organize their activities and actions within a common framework – NODES' Booster Methodology
Spoke Coordinator	The University in charge of coordinating the Spoke's ecosystem. It refers to "Spoke" in the MUR's Call of proposal for "Ecosistemi di Innovazione"
Spoke Data Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the monitoring and management of data generated at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Data Manager.
Spoke Partner	The entity associated to the Spoke Coordinator. It can be an Innovation Cluster, Competence Center, Research Center related to the Spoke's ecosystem and contributes to achieve objectives and impact under the Spoke' leadership and management. It refers to "soggetti affiliati" in the MUR's Call of proposal for "Ecosistemi di Innovazione".
Spoke Project manager	The person who will be the responsible for the management, coordination and progress of the project at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Project Manager.
Spoke research and innovation program	NODES' Research and Innovation program is articulated in specific programs for each Spokes. The spoke will leverage a consolidated collaboration with leading private and public companies and will focus the applied research activity on technological domains and applications that can favour the integration of SMEs into new value chains.
Spoke Scientific and Technical Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the overall scientific contents of the project at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Scientific and Technical Manager.
Spoke Stakeholders Committee (SC)	Consultation structure formed by relevant stakeholders (Government, universities, companies, civil society, third sector, etc.)
Spoke Thematic	General target focus and domain of the Spoke research.
Spoke Topics	Specific areas/lines of development within the Spoke.
Spoke Work Package Leader	At the Spoke level, Work Packages (WPs) will be organized by WP leaders, who will be responsible for performance evaluation and reporting.
Flagship Project	Main research project at the Spoke level with the goal of prototyping, testing, demonstrating the research activities towards higher TRLs.

Table 1 - List of Deliverables

NUM	OUTPUTS/DELIVERABLE NAME	TYPE*	SHORT DESCRIPTION	LEAD PARTICIPANT	DISSEMINATION LEVEL **	DUE DATE
D7.1	Data on type, quality, availability, and geographical distribution of agro-forest waste and by-products	R	Report and a database on distribution and availability of biomass suitable for valorization	UNIBAS	PU	M12
D7.2	Delivery of validated extraction protocols according to the treated biomass type	R	Report on validated methodologies for value-added extracts depending on biomass type	UNIBAS	PU	M22
D7.3	Extracts and pure compounds suitable for pharmaceutical, nutraceutical, cosmetic applications	Other (material)		UNIBAS	PU	M26
D7.4	Extracts suitable as biopesticides	Other (material)		UNIBAS	PU	M26
D7.5	Report on bio-chemical characterization of biomass extracts and pure compounds	R		UNIBAS	PU	M28
D7.6	Biomaterials for bioactive extracts delivery	Other (material)		UNIBAS	PU	M26
D7.8	Formulates for pharmaceutical, nutraceutical, cosmetic applications (in collaboration with companies)	Other (material)		UNIBAS	PU	M28
D7.9	Formulates for agro-chemical applications (in collaboration with companies)	Other (material)		UNIBAS	PU	M28
D7.10	Protocol for scale-up production of valuable bioactive mixtures and compounds from agro-forest waste and by-products	R	Report on validated methodologies suitable for scale-up and industrial production	UNIBAS	PU	M30

Table 2 - List of Project Milestones

MILESTONE NUMBER	MILESTONE NAME	RELATED WORK MODULES	DUE DATE (MONTH)	MEANS OF VERIFICATION
M7.1	Survey on regional scale of the type, quality, availability, distribution of biomass from agro-forest waste	7	8	Report
M7.2	Selection of biomass materials suitable for valorization (at least three)	7	10	Report
M7.3	Validation of extraction protocols for selected matrices and materials	7	12	Report
M7.4	Availability of biomass extracts (at least five) suitable for bio-activity tests	7	16	Material
M7.5	Production of a report on bioactivity of different materials and compounds	7	20	Report
M7.6	Availability of biomaterials for bioactive material delivery	7	26	Material
M7.8	Availability of formulates for pharmaceutical, nutraceutical, cosmetic applications	7	28	Material
M7.9	Availability of formulates for agro-chemical applications	7	28	Material
M7.10	Protocol for scale-up production of valuable bioactive mixtures and compounds from agro-forest waste and by-products	7	30	Report

1. INTRODUCTION

The research work of RM7 was focused on the recovery of bioactive materials from biomass waste. In the previous Milestones/Deliverables the identification and extraction of bioactive metabolites from several biomass waste have been described. In particular, the following waste materials have been investigated: grape pomace, pomegranate waste, pistachio waste, chestnut shells, mushroom cultivation waste, etc.. The investigation on the extraction techniques allowed to identify, for these biomasses, the most suitable extraction methods, taking into account the extraction performances and selectivity, the practicality and economy of the process, its environmental impact and its possible application on industrial scale.

Once optimized the extraction processes and characterized the bioactive extracts some methodologies have been investigated for their effective delivery in biomedical/nutraceutical applications. The results of such investigations are described herein.

2. Biomaterials for bioactive extracts delivery

2.1. NANOENCAPSULATION OF GRAPE POMACE POLYPHENOLS

2.1.1 Introduction

The valorization of agricultural by-products is gaining increasing attention as a sustainable strategy to reduce waste and recover high-value bioactive compounds. Grape pomace (GP) is the primary solid by-product of winemaking, consisting mainly of skins, seeds, and stems. Once considered waste, GP is now recognized as a rich source of biologically active molecules, particularly polyphenols, flavonoids, and tannins, which exhibit antioxidant, anti-inflammatory and antimicrobial properties [1].

In particular, several phenolic compounds found in GP, such as resveratrol, catechins, quercetin, and anthocyanins, have shown protective effects against oxidative stress and cellular damage induced by ultraviolet (UV) radiation. These compounds can help counteract UV-induced inflammation, DNA damage, and degradation of the extracellular matrix, making them promising candidates for dermatological and cosmetic applications [2].

However, despite their potential, many of these bioactive compounds suffer from poor water solubility, low chemical stability, and limited bioavailability, which significantly reduce their efficacy in topical applications. To address these challenges, encapsulation strategies are needed.

In this study, the GP extract obtained from *Vitis vinifera* cv. Aglianico, was encapsulated in transferosomes, lipid vesicles composed of phospholipids and edge activators. These

nanocarriers enhance the stability and penetration of active molecules through the skin barrier [3].

2.1.2 Experimental study

Catechin and epicatechin were identified as the most abundant compounds in the GP extract. The entrapment efficiency of the GP-loaded transferosomes was determined by LC-MS, based on the amounts of these two compounds detected in dialyzed and non-dialyzed samples, according to the protocol of Lela *et al.* [4], with slight modifications.

The EE of the GP transferosomes is reported in **Table 1**.

Table 1 Entrapment Efficiency of Grape pomace extract-loaded transferosomes

	Entrapment Efficiency (%)
Catechin	86.27 ± 2.34
Epicatechin	77.23 ± 4.08

Dermal fibroblasts play a central role in maintaining skin structure and function by producing key components of the extracellular matrix. They also regulate wound healing, tissue remodeling, and respond actively to environmental stressors such as UV radiation by modulating inflammatory and oxidative stress pathways. For these reasons, Normal Human Dermal Fibroblasts (NHDF) were used as *in vitro* model.

The MTT assay was employed to evaluate cell viability of GP extract (GPE), GP-loaded transferosomes (T GPE) and empty transferosomes (T).

The MTT assay is a colorimetric method used to assess cell viability based on metabolic activity. Viable cells reduce the yellow tetrazolium salt (MTT) to insoluble purple formazan crystals via mitochondrial dehydrogenase enzyme. The amount of formazan produced, measured spectrophotometrically, is directly proportional to the number of metabolically viable cells.

The effects of different concentrations (1–200 µg/mL) of GPE in solution or in transferosomes, or empty transferosomes on the viability of NHDF cells was evaluated. The cell viability was measured after 24 h of treatment and is presented as a percentage relative to the control group (CTRL), which represents 100% viability (**Figure 1**). While GPE alone did not affect cell viability at any of the tested concentrations, its formulation exhibited cytotoxicity from 50 µg/mL.

Figure 1 Cell viability, evaluated by MTT assay, of Normal Human Dermal Fibroblasts (NHDF) treated for 24 h with different concentrations (1-200 µg/mL) of Grape Pomace extract in solution (GPE) or in transferosomes (T GPE) and empty transferosomes (T). Data are expressed as the means ± SD of three independent experiments (n=3) and were analyzed by one-way ANOVA followed by Tukey's post-hoc test. **p<0.01, ****p<0.0001 vs CTRL (100% of viability).

The protective effects of GPE and T GPE against UVA-induced loss of viability were investigated. NHDF cells were pre-treated with non-toxic concentrations of GPE (1 – 200 µg/mL) and T GPE (1 – 25 µg/mL) for 24 h, and then irradiated with UVA (25 J/cm²) [5] (**Figure 2**).

Figure 2 Cell viability, evaluated by MTT assay of Normal Human Dermal Fibroblasts (NHDF) treated for 24 h with different concentrations (1-200 µg/mL) of Grape Pomace extract (GPE) or different concentration (1 – 25 µg/mL) of its formulation (T GPE) and then irradiated with UVA (25 J/cm²). Data are expressed as the means ± SD of three independent experiments (n=3) and were analyzed by one-way ANOVA followed by Tukey's post-hoc test. ***p<0.001 vs CTRL+ (UVA-irradiated cells), ####p<0.0001 vs CTRL (100% of viability).

GPE showed significant efficacy in reducing cell viability in UVA-exposed cells only at the highest concentration of 200 µg/mL. Conversely, its formulation (T GPE) demonstrated no

significant effect on cell viability at any of the tested concentrations (1-25 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$) when irradiated with UVA.

Further investigations are warranted to elucidate the underlying reasons for the reduced activity of transferosomes loaded with Grape Pomace extract.

2.2. DEVELOPMENT OF BIOACTIVE ELECTROSPUN SCAFFOLDS INCORPORATING BIOACTIVE COMPOUNDS OBTAINED BY EXTRACTION OF AGRI-FORESTAL WASTE

2.2.1 Introduction

Electrospinning is a versatile and widely adopted technique for the fabrication of nonwoven nano- and microfibrous scaffolds, whose architecture closely mimics the extracellular matrix (ECM). This structural similarity has made electrospun fibers particularly valuable in a variety of biomedical applications, including tissue engineering, wound healing, and drug delivery systems [6]. By precisely modulating the chemical composition of the electrospun fibers, it is possible to tailor the material's interaction with biological tissues and control the release kinetics of embedded therapeutic agents.

In this context, the encapsulation of complex natural products within electrospun scaffolds presents a promising approach to harness their intrinsic bioactivity. In this report two examples will be presented:

2.2.2 Encapsulation Of AgNPs Generated onto Chestnut Shell Lignin into PDLLA Electrospun Scaffolds [7]

We report herein the preparation of hybrid materials in which an electrospun scaffold constituted by poly-D,L-lactic acid matrix, to which chitosan or crystalline nanocellulose was added to improve hydrophilicity, was loaded with different amounts of silver(0) nanoparticles (AgNP) generated onto chestnut shell lignin (CSL) (AgNP@CSL). SEM and TEM analyses confirmed the presence of AgNP@CSL (average size 30 nm) on the fibers. Different chemical assays indicated that the AgNP@CSL containing fibers exhibited marked antioxidant properties (EC_{50} 1.6 ± 0.1 mg/mL, DPPH assay), although they were halved with respect to those of the CSL containing fibers, as expected because of the efficient silver ion reduction. All the fibers showed high cytocompatibility toward human mesenchymal stem cells (hMSCs) representative of the self-healing process, and their antibacterial properties were tested against the pathogens *Escherichia coli* (*E. coli*), *Staphylococcus epidermidis*, and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*. Finally, competitive surface colonization as simulated by cocultures of hMSC and *E. coli* showed that AgNP@CSL loaded fibers offered the cells a targeted protection from infection, thus well balancing cytocompatibility and antibacterial properties.

METHODOLOGY:

AgNPs production: Lignin was obtained by DES extraction (Choline/lactic acid/water) from chestnut shell powder. AgNPs were obtained by mechanochemistry mixing AgNO_3 and lignin in a ball mill.

Electrospinning: The preparation of electrospinning solution/suspension was performed by the following general protocol: CSL or AgNP@CSL, if present, were the first components added to the HFP solvent and, after sonication for 10 min, allowed to stand for 2 h at room temperature with stirring. Subsequently, the polymeric additives, Nanocellulose or chitosan, were added and taken under stirring for 2 h. Finally, PDLLA was introduced and stirred overnight. Electrospinning was performed on a Linari Engineering Gamma-High-Voltage generator electrospinning system. The polymer mixtures were loaded into a 10 mL glass syringe with an 18 G stainless-steel needle and then electrospun at 19 kV with a flow rate of 1.0 mL/h of the pump. The target was a round copper plate having 90 mm diameter coated with aluminum foils, and the distance between the collector and the needle was set to 19 cm.

Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM): SEM images were acquired with a voltage of 20 kV and different magnifications after gold sputter-coating on a Philips FEI ESEM XL30 instrument. The diameter of the fibers was evaluated using the ImageJ software supplied with the DiameterJ plug-in.

Swelling Test Analysis: Four pieces from three different scaffolds with the same composition (a total of 12 samples for each mats) were analyzed. Each sample was immersed in 10 mL of milli-Q H₂O at room temperature for 60 min and shaken at 60 rpm on an orbital shaker. Thereafter, they were gently dried on a filter paper to remove the excess of water and weighed on a balance (Gibertini E 154 Model) having a sensitivity of ± 0.0001 g. The water absorbed by each scaffold was calculated according to the following equation: $\text{Swelling}(\%) = (m_w - m_d / m_d) \times 100$ (1) where m_w and m_d are the masses (g) of wet and dry scaffolds, respectively.

TEM Analysis: Samples for TEM imaging were prepared by depositing e-spun fibers onto carbon-coated copper grids (400 mesh) for 35 s to ensure the deposition of only a few fibers onto the grids. AgNPs embedded in the CSL matrix, e-spun PDLLA scaffold (sample E), e-spun PDLLA-h-CSL (sample B), and e-spun PDLLA-h-AgNP@CSL (sample D) were investigated, and the AgNP@CSL sample was analyzed as previously reported. Briefly, a 1 mg/mL HFP solution of AgNP@CSL was treated for 30 min in an ultrasound bath at room temperature, and then 10 mL of the supernatant obtained after the settling of the suspension was deposited on the grid. TEM images were obtained using Fei Tecnai G2 20 Twin transmission electron microscopes at a 100 kV beam intensity.

Figure 3. Schematic outline of the procedure for the preparation of CSL or AgNP@CSL electrospun mats containing CHT or CNCs as additives.

RESULTS:

The chestnut shell lignin (CSL) was recovered employing DESs as green and ecofriendly extraction solvents following a protocol previously described [7]. With the aim of preparing functional bioactive materials containing additives with antibacterial activity for tissue engineering applications, the AgNP@CSL prepared as above were incorporated into e-spun scaffolds (**Figure 3**). Several attempts to get smooth defect-free microfibrillar scaffolds were preliminarily done before the best composition of the mixture for e-spinning was selected. PDLLA was chosen for preparation of electrospun fibers with AgNP@CSL or CSL based on

optimization experiments. Although PDLLA gives rise to homogeneous electrospun scaffolds, its hydrophobicity represents one of the major limitations for most biological applications. To overcome this drawback, in this study, hydrophilic natural polymers polysaccharidic in nature have been selected as additives, in particular, cellulose nanocrystals (CNCs) and CHT. The average diameters of the e-spun fibers were determined by SEM analysis. The diameter of the fibers is affected by the composition of the electrospinning solution. Because the process parameters (distance between tip and collector, applied voltage, flow) are constant, the main parameters that influence fiber diameter are the viscosity and the conductivity of the solution, the first increasing the mean diameter of the produced fibers and the latter reducing it.

Figure 4. SEM images of (1) e-spun PDLLA-CNC scaffold (sample J); (2) e-spun PDLLA-CNCs-*l*-CSL (sample F), (3) e-spun PDLLA-CNCs-*h*-CSL (sample G), (4) PDLLA-CNCs-*l*-AgNP@CSL (sample H), and (5) PDLLA-CNCs-*h*-AgNP@CSL (sample I).

The morphological properties of all prepared scaffolds were then characterized by scanning electron microscopy (SEM) and transmission electron microscopy (TEM). In a representative example in **Figure 4**, the images of the e-spun fibers containing PDLLA-CNCs with CSL (low and high concentration) (H, I) or AgNP@CSL (low and high) (F, G) are reported. When compared to the control (J), the presence of small agglomerates in e-spun fibers, likely due to the presence of lignin or lignin embedding silver nanoparticles, is observed.

Figure 4. TEM images of (1) AgNPs embedded in CSL matrix, (2) e-spun PDLLA scaffold (sample E), (3) e-spun PDLLA-*h*-CSL (sample B), and (4) e-spun PDLLA-*h*-AgNP@CSL (sample D).

To evaluate the influence of the polysaccharide additives CNCs and CHT on water uptake, swelling tests were carried out on the e-spun fibers containing a high concentration of CSL and AgNP@CSL. The data conclude that the high hydrophobicity of PDLLA e-spun scaffolds can be successfully mitigated by embedding the polysaccharides CNCs and CHT.

The scaffolds were tested for evaluating biological activity. In particular the antioxidant, cytocompatibility and the antimicrobial activity were tested.

Conclusions

The study highlights the versatility of electrospun (e-spun) scaffolds, emphasizing their low-cost, tunable properties, and ability to incorporate bioactive compounds for enhanced tissue engineering applications. The research group developed and tested e-spun fibers made from PDLLA with natural additives like chitosan (CHT) and cellulose nanocrystals (CNCs), showing improvements over previously reported hybrid fibers. Incorporating chestnut shell lignin (CSL) provided antioxidant properties, which were partially retained even when used to generate silver nanoparticles (AgNP@CSL) without solvents. All fibers, including those with AgNPs, demonstrated high cytocompatibility with human mesenchymal stem cells (hMSCs), despite known AgNP toxicity. The resulting materials combined structural benefits for cell growth, antioxidant protection, and antimicrobial activity. Notably, fibers with chitosan and AgNP@CSL

selectively inhibited *E. coli* while maintaining hMSC viability, making them promising for tissue healing and implant osteointegration.

2.2.3 Encapsulation of Propolis Extract into PDLLA/Gelatin Scaffolds

Encapsulation of propolis—a resinous substance produced by bees—has attracted significant interest due to its well-documented antioxidant, antibacterial, and anti-inflammatory properties. The chemical composition of propolis is known to vary depending on geographical and environmental factors, with phenolic compounds being its most bioactive constituents [8,9].

To investigate the potential of propolis as a bioactive component in electrospun scaffolds, ethanolic Soxhlet extracts from three beekeeping companies located in the Basilicata region of Italy were prepared and characterized. The extract with the highest total phenolic content was selected for further processing. This extract was incorporated into a polymeric blend of racemic poly-D,L-lactide (PDLA) and gelatin. Gelatin was included in the formulation to improve the hydrophilicity and enhance the bioactive potential of the final scaffold. The prepared mixtures were electrospun to produce fibrous scaffolds, which were subsequently analyzed using scanning electron microscopy (SEM) to assess morphological characteristics and the influence of extract incorporation. Preliminary findings indicate that the inclusion of ethanolic propolis extracts can be successfully achieved without compromising the fiber morphology and may significantly enhance the biological performance of the scaffolds.

These results underscore the feasibility of utilizing natural bioactive extracts, not limited to propolis, in the development of electrospun biomedical scaffolds. The study paves the way for further research into their application in skin tissue regeneration, wound healing and the treatment of dermatological disorders.

METHODOLOGY:

Material

The samples were collected in the period of August -October 2024. The samples were frozen to $-18\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ and then crushed to powder by a blender HGB550 MODEL 36BL29. Solvents were Obtained by Carlo Erba, VWR and Merck. Standards were obtained by ThermoFischer and Merck.

Different protocols of extraction of propolis

Propolis extraction was performed using three different methods: maceration, ultrasound-assisted extraction, and Soxhlet extraction.

Maceration is the most commonly used technique among beekeepers. In this method, 5.0 g of crushed propolis were added to 50 mL of a 75% (v/v) ethanol solution and stirred continuously for 48 hours at room temperature. The resulting extract was then stored at -18°C for 2 hours to facilitate wax precipitation, followed by filtration. The solvent was removed under reduced pressure, yielding 1.4 g of dry extract (27.9% yield).

Ultrasound-assisted extraction (UAE) was performed using a probe sonicator (UP100H Hielscher) with a maximum output power of 100 W. A mixture of 2.0 g of propolis and 20 mL of 75% ethanol (v/v) was placed in a flask, and the ultrasound probe (6 mm diameter) was immersed 1 cm into the solution. Samples were exposed to varying ultrasound power levels (60, 80 or 100 W) and treatment times (15, 30 or 45 minutes). Following sonication, the extracts were centrifuged at 8800 rpm for 10 minutes. The supernatant was stored at 4°C for 12 hours to promote beeswax precipitation, then centrifuged again under the same conditions. The final extract was obtained by evaporating the solvent under reduced pressure.

Soxhlet extraction was carried out following the procedure described by Grassi et al. This method allowed the recovery of distinct fractions, namely wax, balsam, and resin, based on their solubility and polarity.

Spectroscopic analysis of propolis-extracts

The extracts were chemically characterized by NMR, FT-IR and UV spectroscopies.

The propolis extracts from the 3 different producers (12 mg) were solubilized in 700 μl of DMSO- d_6 containing 0.03% TMS as reference standard. 1D and 2D NMR spectra were recorded on a Varian 400 MHz spectrometer equipped with multinucleus probe at 27°C .

For FT-IR spectra acquisition about 1–2% of lyophilized extract was mixed with potassium bromide (KBr), ground to a fine powder and pressed to form a pellet. IR spectra were recorded on a Jasco FTIR-460 spectrometer. Each spectrum is the result of signal-averaging of 256 scans at a resolution of 2 cm^{-1} . All spectra are transmittance spectra obtained after background subtraction.

UV spectra were recorded in ethanol 96% for resin samples or DCM for balsam samples. The extracts were dissolved in the solvent at a concentration of $13\text{ }\mu\text{g/ml}$. The spectra were recorded in the wavelength range of 200 to 500 nm. Total phenolic content (TPC) was measured according to published protocols.

Protocol optimization for the production of Propolis-containing electrospun scaffolds

To produce the electrospun mats, various types of samples were prepared, all containing the resin extracted using the Soxhlet method as the active ingredient. All samples were electrospun under the same conditions: a voltage of 19 kV, a flow rate of 1 mL/h, a collector distance of 19 cm,

and an 18-gauge needle. Extracts were blended with Poly-D,L-lactide (PDLLA) and Polyvinylpyrrolidone (PVP) or gelatin and electrospun to obtain nanofibrous structured matrices.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

Comprehensive analysis of the chemical profile and biological activity of propolis from the Lucanian region of southern Italy is essential for developing propolis-based agents to be proposed for cosmeceutical or pharmaceutical purpose. In order to develop a methodology capable of identifying the chemical components of propolis, three propolis-producing beekeeping companies from different zones of the Lucanian region were selected [10]. These companies produced propolis using collection grids (rather than by scraping) and provided a sample of raw propolis.

Medium scale companies were chosen, all of which practice migratory beekeeping and manage at least 70 hives. Each company was also asked to complete a short questionnaire consisting of 10 questions, aimed at gathering contextual information about the sample. In particular, the questionnaire focused on two key variables known to significantly influence the chemical composition of propolis: the type of local vegetation—especially tree and shrub species—in the collection area, and the species of honeybee used.

Three different extraction methods were applied. Maceration was the simplest extraction methods, usually employed by bee-keepers producing the lowest yield (27.9%) while Soxhlet extraction was the most technical complex method and yielded ca. 70 % of extract. The ultrasonic extraction methods was the most rapid method with extraction yield comparable to Soxhlet extraction.

Propolis extracts from the 3 extraction methodologies were analyzed by 1D ^1H -NMR spectroscopy (**Figure 5**). For propolis analysis, the main advantage of the ^1H NMR (proton nuclear magnetic resonance) method lies in its ability to detect waxes and terpenoids, which are typically not identified by HPLC-UV due to the absence of UV chromophores.

The ^1H NMR spectra of propolis extracts displayed signals corresponding to all major classes of phytochemicals, which were identified based on their characteristic chemical shifts in specific spectral regions[10]. For instance:

- Signals in the 0.5–3.0 ppm range were mainly attributed to terpenoids, steroids, and linear fatty acids originating from wax residues.
- Signals in the 3.5–5.5 ppm region correspond to sugars,
- Signals in the 6.5–8.0 ppm range are typically associated with phenolic compounds.

Additionally, singlets observed between δH 12.0–13.0 ppm are assigned to phenolic protons involved in intramolecular hydrogen bonding, specifically between the hydroxyl group at the C-5 position and the ketone group at the C-4 position in flavonoid molecules.

However, these exchangeable proton signals are only visible when using aprotic deuterated solvents. Among these, DMSO- d_6 (deuterated dimethyl sulfoxide) is the most commonly used solvent, due to its excellent ability to dissolve a wide range of compounds with varying polarities and its effectiveness in revealing exchangeable proton signals—an important feature for the detailed characterization of propolis components [11].

Figure 5: 1D ^1H -NMR spectra of the extract of company 1 performed by maceration (top), sonication (middle) and Soxhlet extraction (bottom). The spectra are recorded in DMSO- d_6 at 27°C.

With the aim of fractionating and simplifying the compositional analysis of the phytochemicals, a more complex Soxhlet extraction protocol was employed. After extraction of more lipophilic compounds by *n*-hexane Soxhlet extraction, two fractions were obtained, namely wax and balsam. On the residue a further ethanol:chloroform (1:1) Soxhlet extraction was performed that yielded 60-67% of extract, namely resin.

In **Figure 6** the extraction yield of three different propolis samples, belonging to different producers, are shown. The corresponding spectra of the resin fractions are shown in **Figure 7**.

Figure 6: Composition of the propolis of 3 different bee-keeper companies as result of Soxhlet extraction.

Figure 7: 1D ^1H -NMR spectra of the resin extracts of the 3 companies obtained by Soxhlet extraction. The spectra were recorded in $\text{DMSO}-d_6$ at 27°C .

The spectra of resin samples were compared to common propolis standard molecules, as flavonoids and phenolacids. The comparison and identification of diagnostic signals as biomarkers were considered in order to define a semi-automated protocol for compositional

determination. Propolis extracts obtained through Soxhlet extraction from three distinct samples exhibited highly similar chemical profiles, as confirmed by NMR spectroscopy, despite variations in their geographical origin and botanical sources. However, total phenolic content (TPC) varied among the samples and showed strong correlation with the data obtained from UV spectrophotometry (**Figure 8**).

Azienda	TPC Balsamo (mg GAE/g)		TPC Resina (mg GAE/g)		TPC medio Balsamo (mg GAE/g)	TPC medio Resina (mg GAE/g)	TPC medio Totale (mg GAE/g)
	Analisi 1	Analisi 2	Analisi 1	Analisi 2			
1	92.3	97.0	226.2	231.0	94.7 ± 3.3	228.6 ± 3.4	323.3 ± 6.7
2	38.8	39.6	147.3	152.1	39.2 ± 0.7	149.7 ± 3.4	188.0 ± 4.0
3	30.9	32.5	113.0	117.8	31.7 ± 1.1	115.4 ± 3.4	147.1 ± 4.5

Figure 8: Total Phenolic content (TPC) of the 3 samples were evaluated by Foulin Ciocolteau test (Top); UV spectra of resin (bottom left) and balsam (bottom right) extracts of the 3 samples.

The extract with the highest phenolic content (323 mg GAE/g extract) was successfully incorporated into electrospun nanostructured scaffolds composed of PDLLA/PVP and PDLLA/gelatin. (**Figure 9**)

Figure 9: Scanning electron microscopy images recorded on different propolis-containing scaffolds.

Conclusions

The presented study witnessed the importance of relying on multiple analytical techniques for the characterization of propolis and the suitability of a technical support to beekeepers to correctly label and valorise their product. Furthermore, a protocol for the encapsulation of bioactive polyphenolic components into nanofibrous structures was implemented, with the aim to produce biomedical device with antimicrobial and antioxidant activity to be proposed for the treatment of skin-related diseases.

3. BIBLIOGRAPHY

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